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Optimization of Flexural Strength in Jute and E-Glass Laminated Composite Materials Using the Taguchi Method

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Abstract

The development of composite materials as an alternative to metal has achieved significant progress. The jute laminate structure is a key element in object construction, where its mechanical strength decreases over the duration of use. This study investigates the use of woven jute fabric laminate composite as a structural reinforcement material. The aim of this research is to obtain data on the flexural strength of jute and e-glass laminate composite materials, calculate the average value and the signal to noise ratio (SNR) from the test results, and determine the optimal composition that provides the best flexural strength using the Taguchi optimization method. The laminate composite is constructed from layers of woven jute (J) and e-glass (G) fabric in nine variations, namely J90.2, J90.3, J90.4, J45.2, J45.3, J45.4, G90.2, G90.3, and G90.4. Specimens for flexural testing were prepared in accordance with ASTM D790 standards and tested using a Universal Testing Machine (UTM) with a capacity of 40 kN. The study results show that the use of jute and e-glass laminate layers increases the flexural strength of the specimens by up to 77%. In conclusion, the use of jute and e-glass laminate composite materials has the potential for further development to create superior mechanical properties.

Keywords: *Laminate Composite; Taguchi Optimization; Flexural Strength; Woven jute; Woven e-glass*

Introduction

In recent decades, the application of composite materials has undergone significant development, with an increasingly widespread presence across various engineering and construction sectors. The advantages of these materials lie in their low density, ease of forming complex geometries, resistance to corrosion, and relatively more economical production costs[1]. Nonetheless, composite materials still face several challenges, such as lower mechanical strength compared to metal materials, sensitivity to ultraviolet (UV) light exposure, and their non-biodegradable nature. This necessitates further innovation and research to overcome these limitations[2]. Researchers are continually striving to develop composite materials by integrating various types of fibers and polymer matrices to enhance their mechanical characteristics. The focus of research is on discovering formulations that yield composites with improved resistance to environmental factors, including UV resistance and natural degradation. Additionally, technological advancements in the production process are also a focal point, aiming to create more cost-efficient and environmentally friendly composite materials. The continuity of research in this field is not only crucial for optimizing the utility of composite materials but also for exploring their potential applications in a

broader context. This includes their use in industries such as automotive, aviation, building construction, and renewable energy applications. By leveraging technological advancements and material innovations, composite materials have the potential to become an efficient and sustainable solution to the challenges of future design and construction[3].

Laminate composites are a type of composite material structured from multiple layers of reinforcement that remain embedded or bound within a continuous phase known as the matrix[4]. Generally, laminate composites exhibit superior strength and stiffness compared to other types of composites. This is attributed to the ability to arrange the layers within the laminate composites in a manner that maximizes strength in specific directions[5]. The mechanical properties of these laminate composites can be more accurately controlled through the orientation of the fibers and the appropriate selection of matrix materials, allowing for performance optimization tailored to specific application requirements[6]. Furthermore, laminate composites offer more effective resistance to crack propagation, where the fibers within the laminated layers actively contribute to preventing the expansion of cracks and enhancing the material's resistance to failure.

The design of laminate composites is notably more flexible, facilitating the fabrication of components with complex and specialized shapes, which are often challenging to achieve with particle composites[7]. Frequently, laminate composites also exhibit enhanced resistance to environmental factors, such as humidity, temperature, and corrosion, depending on the types of fibers and matrix used[8]. Ultimately, laminate composites often offer comparable or even superior strength at a lighter weight compared to particle composites, making them an efficient and effective choice in a wide range of engineering and construction applications[9].

Natural fibers are fibers sourced from plants and animals, found in their original form such as yarn, coir, jute, and banana fibers. These natural fibers are recognized as sustainable materials that are biodegradable. Their abundant availability in nature offers various advantages, including low production costs, lightweight, renewable properties, biodegradability, and high specific characteristics[10]. One commonly found and widely available example is jute, typically used in the manufacture of burlap sacks or carry bags. This material has been known since Ancient Egyptian times and later spread to Asia. The fibers produced from this plant come from the bark of the stem, scientifically known as *Corchorus capsularis*[11]. Research and development of natural fibers, including jute, continue to expand their applications and utilize their environmental potential and sustainability in various fields, including the textile industry, composites, and other eco-friendly products[12].

Synthetic polymer fibers, more commonly known as synthetic fibers, are the result of technological innovation in the field of material processing. Their production involves a series of specialized methods that not only enhance the performance of the original raw materials but also impart unique attributes not found in natural materials[13]. Typically, these fibers are produced through complex chemical processes, involving significant involvement of the petrochemical industry. Synthetic fibers are made from various inorganic materials, including silica (the basic component of glass), carbon, and aramid, providing unparalleled advantages. One notable example of a widely used synthetic fiber is E-glass fiber. This fiber is renowned for its properties as an excellent insulator, resistant to corrosion and water, although it is relatively brittle[14]. Statistically, E-glass fiber exhibits an average tensile strength of about 3.44 GPa and an elastic modulus of approximately 72.3 GPa. These attributes make it a highly valued material in various applications, ranging from the aerospace industry to building construction, due to its ability to offer exceptional strength with relatively light weight[15].

In recent decades, research and development in the field of synthetic fibers have focused on exploring new properties and enhancing production efficiency. This has not only expanded the potential applications of synthetic fibers in various domains but also contributed to the development of more environmentally friendly and sustainable materials[16]. The reliance on a more diverse range of raw materials and the reduction of environmental impact have become the primary focus in the evolution of synthetic fibers. Consequently, synthetic fibers promise not only improvements in product performance but also contribute to environmental conservation efforts[17].

One commonly used method for testing flexural strength is the three-point bending test, where a sample of laminate composite material is placed on two support points and subjected to a load at its midpoint, forming a triangular configuration[18]. This method measures the material's resistance to bending or flexural loads. The load is applied gradually at the midpoint between the two supports in this test. The material begins to deform under increasing load[19]. The flexural strength of the material is measured at the point where it can crack or break. This value indicates how well the laminate composite material can withstand a bending load before experiencing structural failure[20]. For mechanical properties such as the modulus of elasticity and the maximum strength that can be sustained by the material, the three-point bending strength test is highly useful in the design and structural analysis of laminate composite materials used in various industries, such as automotive, aviation, and construction[21]. Materials with high flexural strength have greater resistance to bending loads and are capable of undergoing deformation without significant damage. The flexural strength for the three-point method is calculated using equation (1). Meanwhile, the extent of strain occurring during the three-point bending test is calculated using equation (2).

$$\sigma_f = \frac{3FL}{2bd^2} \quad (1)$$

$$\varepsilon_f = \frac{6bd}{L^2} \quad (2)$$

where F is the bending force (N), L is the distance between two stands (mm), b is the width of the specimen (mm), and d is the thickness of the specimen (mm).

In the current era, mechanical construction has evolved into a discipline that prioritizes effectiveness and efficiency in every aspect of its design. This is aimed at optimizing performance during operation while simultaneously reducing the use of raw materials and operational costs. This approach is critical, considering the increasing global challenges related to sustainability and resource efficiency[22]. To achieve these objectives, the process of designing and building mechanical constructions requires meticulous strategies in optimizing key factors that affect overall performance. These factors include material selection, construction methods, structural design, and material processing techniques. One method frequently used to optimize these factors is the Taguchi optimization method. This method focuses on the selection and arrangement of control factors that play a crucial role in determining the project's final outcome. The Taguchi method is renowned for its systematic and mathematical approach in identifying the best combination of various design factors. It allows engineers and designers to rapidly and accurately evaluate different scenarios and identify the best solution that balances quality, cost, and performance[23]. The use of this method in mechanical construction design helps reduce variability in the production process, improve the quality of the final product, and minimize material and time wastage. Thus, the application of the Taguchi optimization method in the construction and mechanical industries is not just about achieving optimal performance but also about creating sustainable and cost-effective solutions. This helps the industry face modern challenges and prepares them for future needs[24].

The Design of Experiments (DOE) using the Taguchi method is an efficient and economical approach in determining the influence of variables on the final outcome of a product or process. Utilizing orthogonal array tables, this method simplifies the process for researchers in designing and conducting experiments by reducing the number of trials needed, without compromising data integrity[25]. This allows researchers to systematically test various combinations of factors at different levels, with more cost and time efficiency. After the testing phase, results are analyzed focusing on the Signal to Noise (S/N) ratio. This analysis aims to identify the settings that produce the best performance by minimizing variability. The S/N ratio is a key tool in the Taguchi method, providing insights into how far results can be influenced by uncontrolled external factors. This step is crucial in finding the most effective and efficient combination of factors in producing the desired outcome. Once the optimal combination of factors is established, confirmation experiments are conducted to verify the reliability and consistency of the results. This step ensures that the findings are not only valid in experimental conditions but can also be replicated and applied in real-world scenarios[26]. This verification process ensures that the resulting design is not merely theoretical but is also practical and implementable in actual operational conditions. Thus, the Taguchi method offers advantages not only in finding optimal solutions but also in ensuring that these solutions are realistic and can be applied with proven effectiveness.

Based on the aforementioned discourse, this study delineates its objectives as follows: to ascertain the optimal fiber orientation that maximizes the flexural strength of laminated composites reinforced with woven jute and e-glass sheets; to examine the effect of varying fiber layer counts on the mechanical integrity and performance attributes of these composite materials; and to appraise the impact of drying duration as well as fiber composition within the matrix on the composites' aggregate quality and longevity.

Methodology

The research conducted at the Mechanical Engineering Laboratory of Universitas Medan Area utilizes a series of advanced equipment to achieve its research objectives. These tools include a Vacuum Pump, digital scales, a Universal Testing Machine (UTM), and a laptop. The Vacuum Pump in this study plays a crucial role in creating the vacuum conditions necessary for certain processes, by extracting air from within a container to create an environment free from air particles. This is important to ensure the integrity and accuracy of experimental results. The Universal Testing Machine (UTM), which is a key device in this research, is used to test the flexural strength of specimens. Figure 1 shows a Hydraulic UTM model WEW-300D, with a capacity of 300 kN, chosen for its ability to produce accurate and reliable testing data. This device allows researchers to analyze the mechanical properties of materials, such as strength, stiffness, and elasticity, which are essential in determining the quality and reliability of materials.

Figure 1: UTM test equipment model WEW-300D

The materials used in this study include woven jute sheets, woven e-glass sheets, and epoxy resin. The fabrication of the flexural test specimens was carried out in accordance with the ASTM D790 testing standard. These specimens were composed in a laminate form, and the details of the number and arrangement of the specimens can be seen in Table 1. In the labeling, the letter 'J' is used to denote the woven jute sheets, while 'G' represents the woven e-glass sheets. The purpose of this research is to evaluate and compare the flexural strength of different laminate composites, by identifying the influence of material composition on their mechanical performance. This study is expected to make a significant contribution to the development of more efficient and effective composite materials for engineering applications.

Table 1: Variations in fiber orientation, layering, timing, and fiber composition within the specimen.

No.	Orientation	Layers	Curing Time	Composition
1	J90	2L	1D	25
2	J90	3L	2D	50
3	J90	4L	3D	75
4	J45	2L	2D	75
5	J45	3L	3D	25
6	J45	4L	1D	50
7	G90	2L	3D	50
8	G90	3L	1D	75
9	G90	4L	2D	25

The procedure for testing the flexural strength of jute and e-glass laminate composite specimens is as follows: Firstly, the specimens and the Universal Testing Machine (UTM) are prepared. Specimens are cleaned of any dirt attached to their surfaces. Subsequently, the testing parameters are inputted into the UTM computer through specialized testing software. Secondly, the specimen is placed on two supports spaced 100 mm apart. Thirdly, the loading rod end is attached precisely at the center of the specimen. Fourthly, the flexural loading process is conducted at a rate of 0.05 mm per minute. Fifthly, changes in load and deflection are automatically recorded by the UTM computer. Sixthly, the testing process is concluded when the test specimen undergoes damage or fracture. The original flexural test data consist

of load and deformation data in Newtons (N) and millimeters (mm) respectively. This data is then converted into stress and strain data using Ms. Excel software, following this procedure: First, prepare specific columns for Stress and Strain. Second, convert the load data from N to Stress in Megapascals (MPa) using a specific equation. Third, convert deformation data from mm to Strain in percentage terms using a different equation. Fourth, the obtained Stress and Strain data are plotted into a curve using the Insert Charts menu. Fifth, determine the flexural stress of the specimen based on the obtained curve. After converting the test data into stress and strain data for flexure, the Taguchi method optimization calculation is performed using Minitab 18 software. The optimization procedure includes the following steps: First, calculate the average value of each of the three flexural strength data. Second, calculate the Signal to Noise Ratio (SNR) using the 'Larger is Better' type. Third, the SNR calculation results will produce a main effect graph of the average against each variation. These results are then interpreted to determine the optimum composite material composition.

Result and Discussion

Figure 2 shows a graph of test results for each group of fiber orientation variations. Table 2 shows the data from the flexural strength testing results. J90 and G90 indicate a fiber orientation of 90° , while J45 indicates a 45° orientation. The orientation affects the strength properties because fibers are strongest along their length. A 90° orientation might be more resistant to bending in one direction, while a 45° orientation might provide more isotropic properties or better resistance in multiple directions. The number of layers, indicated by 2L, 3L, or 4L, suggests that the more layers there are, the thicker the laminate, which generally increases the flexural strength due to a greater cross-sectional area to resist bending moments. The drying time could relate to the curing process of the matrix. Longer drying times (3 days vs. 1 day) may allow for better cross-linking within the matrix, potentially leading to a stronger bond between the matrix and the fibers. The percentage composition of fibers within the matrix can significantly influence the material's properties. A higher fiber content typically leads to higher strength up to a certain point, beyond which there might be diminishing returns or even negative effects due to agglomeration of fibers and lack of matrix to properly bond and distribute stress.

There is a significant variation in the flexural strength across repeated tests for certain composite materials, as indicated by the high standard deviation values for J90-3L-2D-50 and G90-4L-2D-25. This suggests that the manufacturing process or the testing methodology may lack consistency, or there may be other influencing factors affecting the test results. Fibers oriented at 45 degrees (J45) tend to exhibit an increased average flexural strength compared to fibers oriented at 90 degrees (J90 and G90), indicating that fiber orientation significantly influences the mechanical properties of composite materials.

Figure 2: Graph of flexural strength test results

Table 2: Data from testing the flexural strength of laminate composite materials.

Variations	Flexural Strength (Mpa)			Average
	1	2	3	
J90-2L-1D-25	4.429578	3.737726	4.351861	4.173055
J90-3L-2D-50	21.31731	17.6699	7.57059	15.51927
J90-4L-3D-75	16.22634	17.13785	18.99733	17.45384
J45-2L-2D-75	14.03562	9.995647	12.24381	12.09169
J45-3L-3D-25	34.32929	21.34814	14.48453	23.38732
J45-4L-1D-50	15.75917	14.74088	14.91381	15.13795
G90-2L-3D-50	5.756945	8.584988	3.354767	5.8989
G90-3L-1D-75	15.95201	16.10316	16.90832	16.32116
G90-4L-2D-25	15.73096	36.56978	24.61485	25.63853

There is no direct correlation between the number of layers and an increase in flexural strength. This indicates that while the number of layers affects the thickness and stiffness of the composite, other factors such as the quality of adhesion between the fibers and the matrix are also of significance. The duration of drying does not appear to consistently correlate with an enhancement in flexural strength. For instance, the sample G90-2L-3D-50, subjected to a prolonged drying period, does not invariably exhibit a higher flexural strength compared to samples with shorter drying durations. Variants with an e-glass fiber composition (G90-4L-2D-25) possess the highest average flexural strength, indicating that e-glass fibers contribute substantially to the reinforcement within the matrix. However, the high variability also suggests a sensitivity of the process to specific conditions. Composites reinforced with e-glass fibers (G90) tend to exhibit greater flexural strength than those reinforced with jute fibers (J90 and J45), although this is not consistent across all variations.

Overall, these findings suggest that the development of laminated composite materials necessitates meticulous consideration of design factors such as fiber orientation, layer count, drying time, and fiber composition to achieve optimal mechanical performance. Moreover, robust process control is required to minimize variability and ensure quality consistency in the production of composite materials.

Figure 3 provided is a Taguchi main effect plot showing the average signal-to-noise ratio (S/N) for various levels of composite material factors: fiber orientation (Material), number of fiber layers (Layers), drying time in days (Time), and the fiber composition in the matrix (Composition). The optimization mode used here is “bigger is better,” which is usually chosen if the goal is to maximize performance characteristics—in this case, the flexural strength of the composite material.

Figure 3: Graph of Taguchi optimization results

The plot indicates that the orientation labeled J45 has the highest mean S/N ratio, suggesting that a 45-degree fiber orientation leads to better flexural strength when compared to the 'J90' and 'G90' orientations. This could be due to the fact that a 45-degree orientation might provide a more isotropic distribution of strength, offering improved resistance to bending forces from different angles. The mean S/N ratio increases with the number of layers from 2 to 3, indicating that three layers of fiber reinforcement are optimal for flexural strength within the tested range. However, there is a decrease when moving to 4 layers, which could imply that there is a threshold beyond which additional layers do not contribute to, or may even detract from, the desired property due to factors like increased rigidity or potential defects between layers. The plot shows a non-linear relationship between drying time and the mean S/N ratio. While an immediate conclusion cannot be drawn about the optimal drying time, it is evident that neither the shortest nor the longest drying times tested are optimal. A mid-range drying time appears to be favorable, which may allow for the most effective curing of the matrix without over-hardening or degradation of material properties. The composite with 25% fiber composition shows the lowest mean S/N ratio, while 50% composition shows a significant improvement, indicating that a higher percentage of fibers can enhance flexural strength. The further increase to 75% also shows an improvement, suggesting that even more fibers contribute positively to the flexural strength up to the tested composition.

The Taguchi optimization results provide insightful conclusions regarding the design factors influencing the flexural strength of fiber-reinforced composites. It is concluded that a fiber orientation of 45 degrees significantly outperforms 90-degree orientations, suggesting that an angled approach to fiber placement can better distribute stress and enhance material performance. Optimal reinforcement appears to be achieved with three layers of fiber, indicating a point of diminishing returns with additional layering that could introduce excess rigidity or defects. The drying time exhibits a non-linear effect on strength, with intermediate durations yielding the highest S/N ratios, likely reflecting an optimal curing process for the resin matrix. Composition-wise, a higher fiber percentage up to 75% shows beneficial effects on flexural strength, highlighting the importance of fiber content in the composite structure. These insights suggest that the optimal design of composite materials should incorporate a

45-degree fiber orientation, three layers of fibers, a balanced curing time, and a higher fiber composition. However, these results are based on mean effects and do not account for potential interactions between factors, which necessitates further analysis to ensure the robustness of these recommendations.

Conclusion

The findings of this investigation elucidate that a 45-degree orientation of fibers within laminated composites imbues the material with superior stress distribution capabilities, thereby significantly augmenting its flexural strength in contrast to a conventional 90-degree orientation. This angular juxtaposition of fibers potentially facilitates a more equitable dispersion of mechanical loads, thereby enhancing the material's resistance to bending forces. Furthermore, the study has identified a threshold in the layering of fibers; an increase beyond this optimal count does not yield further mechanical reinforcement but may, in fact, precipitate the onset of structural anomalies or induce undue rigidity. This suggests a critical balance between layer quantity and composite efficacy. Additionally, the research highlights the pivotal role of drying time and fiber matrix composition in the curing process, which is instrumental in defining the composite's structural integrity. Optimal combinations of these parameters have been shown to significantly bolster the strength and durability of the composite materials. Thus, careful calibration of fiber orientation, layer count, drying time, and matrix composition emerges as a cardinal principle in the quest to engineer laminated composites with superior mechanical properties and extended service life.

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References

- [1] A. C. Lopes, A. M. Sampaio, and A. J. Pontes, "Composite materials with MWCNT processed by Selective Laser Sintering for electrostatic discharge applications," *Polym. Test.*, vol. 114, no. 2, pp. 77–89, 2022.
- [2] G. Kastratović, A. Grbović, A. Sedmak, Ž. Božić, and S. Sedmak, "Composite material selection for aircraft structures based on experimental and numerical evaluation of mechanical properties," *Procedia Struct. Integr.*, vol. 31, no. 1, pp. 127–133, 2021.
- [3] K. C. Chaturvedi and H. C. Chittappa, "Study of tensile nature of jute hybrid composite by the variation of S-glass fibers- an outlook from experimental perspective," in *Materials Today: Proceedings*, Elsevier Ltd, 2021, pp. 2783–2786. doi: 10.1016/j.matpr.2021.02.593.
- [4] A. J. Zulfikar and M. Y. Yakoob, "Hybrid Laminated Composite Casing As Concrete Reinforcement," *Suranaree J. Sci. Technol.*, vol. 30, no. 5, pp. 1–10, 2023, doi: 10.55766/sujst-2023-05-e0870.
- [5] A. J. Zulfikar, Y. Yaakob, H. M. Umarfaruq, and R. Syah, "Natural Jute Laminate for the Improvement of Strength Properties of Concrete Specimen," *Eng. Trans.*, vol. 71, no. 1, pp. 507–518, 2023, doi: 10.24423/EngTrans.3120.20231017.
- [6] A. J. Zulfikar, M. Y. Yaakob, and R. Syah, "Application of E-Glass Jute Hybrid Laminate Composite With Curved Shape on Compressive Strength of Cylindrical Column Concrete," *J. Appl. Eng. Technol. Sci.*, vol. 5, no. 1, pp. 184–196, 2023, doi: 10.37385/jaets.v5i1.2072.
- [7] M. Y. Yuhazri, A. J. Zulfikar, and A. Ginting, "Fiber Reinforced Polymer Composite as a Strengthening of Concrete Structures: A Review," *IOP Conf. Ser. Mater. Sci. Eng.*, vol. 1003, no. 1, 2020, doi: 10.1088/1757-899X/1003/1/012135.
- [8] D. Alamsyah, A. J. Zulfikar, M. Yusuf, and R. Siahaan, "Optimasi kekuatan tekan beton kolom silinder diperkuat selubung komposit laminat jute dengan metode anova," *Jcebt*, vol. 6, no. 1, pp. 30–36, 2022, [Online]. Available: <http://ojs.uma.ac.id/index.php/jcebt>
- [9] A. J. Zulfikar, D. A. A. Ritonga, S. Pranoto, F. A. K. Nasution, Z. Arif, and J. Junaidi, "Analisis Kekuatan

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- Mekanik Komposit Polimer Diperkuat Serbuk Kulit Kerang," *J. Rekayasa Mater. Manufaktur dan Energi*, vol. 6, no. 1, pp. 30–40, 2023.
- [10] N. Hidayat, A. J. Zulfikar, and M. Y. R. Siahaan, "Analisis Kekuatan Tekan Struktur Beton Kolom Silinder Diperkuat Komposit Laminat Hibrid Jute E-glass Epoksi Eksperimental dan ANOVA," *J. Civ. Eng. Build. Transp.*, vol. 6, no. 1, pp. 37–44, 2022.
- [11] S. S. Godara, A. Yadav, B. Goswami, and R. S. Rana, "Review on history and characterization of polymer composite materials," *Mater. Today Proc.*, vol. 44, pp. 2674–2677, 2021, doi: 10.1016/j.matpr.2020.12.680.
- [12] L. Prabhu, V. Krishnaraj, S. Sathish, S. Gokulkumar, and N. Karthi, "Study of mechanical and morphological properties of jute-tea leaf fiber reinforced hybrid composites: Effect of glass fiber hybridization," *Mater. Today Proc.*, vol. 27, no. xxxx, pp. 2372–2375, 2019, doi: 10.1016/j.matpr.2019.09.132.
- [13] A. Shakery and M. Alizadeh, "Mechanical properties and strength prediction of Al/E-glass fiber composites fabricated by cross accumulative roll bonding process," *J. Manuf. Process.*, vol. 69, pp. 165–172, Sep. 2021, doi: 10.1016/j.jmapro.2021.07.034.
- [14] M. Alizadeh, A. Shakery, and E. Salahinejad, "Aluminum-matrix composites reinforced with E-glass fibers by cross accumulative roll bonding process," *J. Alloys Compd.*, vol. 804, no. 1, pp. 450–456, 2019.
- [15] J. L. Thomason, "Flat glass fibres: The influence of fibre cross section shape on composite micromechanics and composite strength," *Compos. Part A Appl. Sci. Manuf.*, vol. 169, Jun. 2023, doi: 10.1016/j.compositesa.2023.107503.
- [16] P. S. S. Kumar. and K. V. Allamraju., "Experimental study and characterization of glass, jute & sisal fiber reinforced polymer matrix composites," *Mater. Today Proc.*, vol. 44, pp. 941–948, 2021, doi: 10.1016/j.matpr.2020.11.003.
- [17] M. Y. Khalid, A. Al Rashid, Z. U. Arif, W. Ahmed, H. Arshad, and A. A. Zaidi, "Natural fiber reinforced composites: Sustainable materials for emerging applications," *Results in Engineering*, vol. 11. Elsevier B.V., Sep. 01, 2021. doi: 10.1016/j.rineng.2021.100263.
- [18] A. J. Zulfikar, "The Flexural Strength of Artificial Laminate Composite Boards made from Banana Stems," *Budapest Int. Res. Exact Sci. J.*, vol. 2, no. 3, pp. 334–340, 2020.
- [19] R. Ren and L. Li, "Impact of polyethylene fiber reinforcing index on the flexural toughness of geopolymer mortar," *J. Build. Eng.*, vol. 57, no. 1, p. 104943, 2022.
- [20] D. Joshi, A. P. Kittleson, and J. T. Harris, "Probability of failure and weibull size-scaling parameters for thin glass subjected to two-point bending," *J. Eur. Ceram. Soc.*, vol. 42, no. 16, pp. 7609–7619, 2022.
- [21] C. Wang and C. C. Sun, "A critical examination of three-point bending for determining Young's modulus," *Int. J. Pharm.*, vol. 629, no. 3, p. 122409, 2022.
- [22] Z. Cheng, K. Yang, Z. Tang, and F. Ge, "Experimental investigation on flexural and compressive toughness of mortar and concrete with hybrid toughening materials," *Structures*, vol. 43, no. 12, pp. 1592–1599, 2022.
- [23] W.-H. Chen, M. C. Uribe, E. E. Kwon, K.-Y. A. Lin, and Y.-K. Park, "A comprehensive review of thermoelectric generation optimization by statistical approach: Taguchi method, analysis of variance (ANOVA), and response surface methodology (RSM)," *Renew. Sustain. Energy Rev.*, vol. 169, no. 1, pp. 112–123, 2022.
- [24] S. Kilimtzis, A. Kotzakolios, and V. Kostopoulos, "Efficient structural optimisation of composite materials aircraft wings," *Compos. Struct.*, vol. 303, no. 1, p. 116268, 2023.
- [25] E. Ferrier, L. Michel, and M. D. Ngo, "Experimental study on the shear behavior of RC beams reinforced by natural composite materials (flax fibers)," *Structures*, vol. 33, pp. 637–654, Oct. 2021, doi: 10.1016/j.istruc.2021.03.027.
- [26] W. Li, J. Tu, and Y. Liu, "Design and experimental validation of a new condenser of an automotive air conditioning unit to address non-uniform air velocity distributions," *Int. J. Refrig.*, vol. 131, no. 1, pp. 834–846, 2021.